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**METHODS FOR INCREASING MECHANICAL AND PERFORMANCE
PROPERTIES OF PARTS FROM ALLOYED HIGH CHROMIUM WHITE
CAST IRON**

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Today, one of the most important world tasks is to increase the economic efficiency of parts produced by casting from white cast iron by increasing their operational and mechanical properties. One of the important tasks is to conduct scientific research in this area, including in such areas as: development of the composition of the alloy using modern software, taking into account the operating conditions of wear-resistant white cast iron; optimization of white cast iron casting processes; the need to develop new optimal methods of heat treatment.

At the metallurgical enterprises of the developed countries of the world ferrous metallurgy, a number of research works are being carried out to obtain high-quality castings from wear-resistant white cast irons, in particular, wear-resistant chromium cast irons. The USA, Russia, Germany, Great Britain, Canada, Brazil, Japan, Australia, Ukraine, Poland, India, China, Belarus, Iran, Mexico and other countries are the leading producers of white cast iron, producing 60-70% of the world's parts.

The chemical composition of samples of white cast irons ICH280Kh29NL and ICH300Kh32N2M2TL used for crushing ores in NMMC is given. Samples made in sand molds, as well as samples cut from imported parts made of white cast iron ASTM A 532, were chosen as the object of study. The chemical composition of the samples

used in the research materials was analyzed on Spectro-Lab-M model spectral equipment in the central laboratory NMMC PO NMZ (Table 1).

Samples of wear-resistant white cast iron underwent heat treatment in a laboratory muffle furnace model SNOL 3/11 and in an industrial electric furnace model H-85. Microstructural studies were carried out using a TESCAN MIRA scanning electron microscope with a magnification of 500 to 5000 times at the National Research Technological University MISiS (NITU MISiS, Russia) and an OLYMPUS BX53 optical microscope at the central research laboratory of NMMC with a magnification of 200 to 1000 times.

Table 1

Chemical composition of cast iron grades 280Cr29NiL, 300Cr32Ni2Mo2TiL and ASTM A 532

№	Cast iron grades	Chemical amounts of elements, % by weight									
		C	Si	Cr	Mo	V	Mn	Ni	Ti	P	S
1.	280Cr29NiL	2,82	0,6	28,23	-	0,02	0,46	1,5	-	0,062	0,03
2.	300Cr32Ni2Mo2TiL	2,60	1,2	32,0	1,7	-	0,54	2,1	0,4	0,067	0,03
3.	ASTM A532*	2,88	0,6	28,26	0,2	-	1,38	0,6	0,02	0,025	0,02

***Interpreted values are based on regulatory documents.**

As an object of study, chemical elemental analysis, surface distribution and microstructural analysis of white cast irons ICH280X29NL, ICH300X32N2M2TL and ASTM A532 were performed. Special samples were made to determine the mechanical properties of white cast iron. To determine the strength of the specimens in bending, a universal testing machine GMS-50 was used, to determine the impact strength - a pendulum MK-30A, to determine the rigidity - a device for determining the rigidity TK-2M (table 2).

Table 2

Mechanical properties of white cast irons 280Cr29NiL, 300Cr32Ni2Mo2TiL and ASTM A 532

Cast iron grades	Impact strength, KV, J/cm ²		Redistribution of bending strength, σ_v , MPa		Hardness, HRC ₃	
	Measured- ny	According to GOST	Measured- ny	According to GOST	Measured- ny	According to GOST
280Cr29NiL	10,9-11,2	11,1	398	405	43-44	46
300Cr32Ni2Mo2TiL	9,7-9,8	9,8	432	441	56-57	55
ASTM A532*	8,5		460		58-60	57

***Interpreted values are based on regulatory documents.**

An analysis of the phases by multicomponent state diagrams based on Fe-C is given. The TCFE7 database of the Thermo-Calc software, updated in May 2018, which is the software of Thermo-Calc Software (Sweden), was used in the construction and analysis of two-, three- and multicomponent thermodynamic state diagrams based on the Fe-C system. Based on the chemical composition of white cast iron grades ICH280Kh29NL, ICH300Kh32N2M2TL and ASTM A532, studied as an object of study, more than 50 thermodynamic state diagrams with three, four and many components were constructed using the Thermo-Calc program. Diagrams of thermodynamic state in Fe-2.6C-Cr-Ni, Fe-2.6C-Cr-Mn, Fe-2.6C-Cr-Si, Fe-2.6C-Cr-Ti and many systems based on white ICH280X29NL cast iron studied. According to him, the types of metal bases and carbides formed in the structure with a change in the amount of Cr, Ni, Mn, Si and Ti elements in the alloy were studied.

The types of carbides in high-alloyed white cast irons have been established. It was found that as the number of alloying elements increases, compounds with the following stoichiometric ratio of components can form in the alloys: M₃C, M₆C, M₅C₂, M₇C₃, M₂₃C₆. For the first time, the effect of directional crystallization of complex alloyed carbides was obtained.

During the production process, as a result of simplifying the chemical composition of white cast iron, alloying elements, including ferrochromium, were saved by 40%, nickel by 45%, and all other chemical elements by an average of 10-20%. % per 1 ton of produced alloy. As a result of the use of casting processes and optimal heat treatment standards in the manufacture of the supplier's disk parts, the

service life of the parts has been increased by at least 20%, and the cost of the parts has been reduced by 30%.

List of sources used

1. Youping, M., Xiulan, L., Yugao, L., Shuyi, Z. and Xiaoming, D., Microstructure and properties of Ti–Nb–V–Mo-alloyed high chromium cast iron, *Bull. Mater. Sci.*, 36, pp. 839-844, 2013.
2. Zhou, S., Shen, Y., Zhang, H. and Chen, D., Heat treatment effect on microstructure, hardness and wear resistance of Cr26 white cast iron”, *Chinese Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 28, pp. 141-147, 2015.
3. Yilmaz, S. O. and Tanju, T., Effect of TiBAI inoculation and heat treatment on microstructure and mechanical properties of hypereutectic high chromium white cast iron, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 672, pp. 324-331, 2016.
4. W. Wołczyński, E. Guzik, B. Kania, W. Wajda: Structures field in the solidifying cast iron roll. *Archives of Foundry Engineering*, vol. 10 (2010) 41-46.
5. W. Wołczyński, E. Guzik, W. Wajda, D. Jędrzejczyk et al.: CET in Solidifying Roll – Thermal Gradient Field Analysis *Archives of Metallurgy and Materials*, 57, (2012) , 105-117.